

Towards a User-friendly and Dependable Wireless Sensor Node Application for Weather Monitoring

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Abstract— this paper proposes a design idea of automatic weather station. The system shall involve the implementation of drivers for capturing temperature, relative humidity, pressure and performing analog to digital conversions using SHT25, MS5611 and MCP3424 sensors respectively. They shall be open source providing additional functionalities missing in the proprietary firmware. The data (temperature, relative humidity and pressure) shall be collected through the use of radio wireless sensor nodes (RSS2). The collected data shall be transmitted to the remote server. This data shall be accessed remotely by means of accessing the server via its IP address on to which the sink node shall be attached. This data shall be manipulated and used for forecasting purposes. The system shall include a graphic user interface application (SensorReader) that shall be used to access and store data on the server.

Index Terms—Automatic Weather Station, MS5611, Raspberry pi, SensorReader, SHT25, Sink node, SSH client, Wireless sensor node.

I. INTRODUCTION

Weather is changing at rates unprecedented, therefore changing the lives of billions of people. The impacts of weather changes will continue to have grave implications on the lifestyle and economic activities, therefore presenting one of the greatest challenges

affecting the world today. Extreme weather events are on the increase, resulting into occurrences such as drought and floods [1], which may lead to extinctions, widespread hunger, mass displacements, disease epidemics and other catastrophic results. Communities whose livelihood is tightly bound to weather are more prone to these

implications. In Uganda, 80% of the population depends on rain fed agriculture; pastoralists depend on rain for fresh pasture and water for their animals while farmers depend on rain to determine when to plant and harvest their crops.

We designed an AWS with an objective of improving robustness and affordability but most importantly address the unique needs for Africa. The AWS uses radio sensor nodes[9], which wirelessly collect weather information and transmit it to a repository via a gateway, a device connected to the Internet. The node runs a proprietary application, giving no room for customization of functions to suit our unique needs. The unique challenges called for the introduction of a free and open source software. This system comprises of majorly two components namely SensorReader application which is a replacement for sensd, a command line application and also sensor drivers.

In order to produce a robust and affordable AWS, we aim to give control of software in the hands of Africans by providing free and open source code, which is understood by many, hence lowering costs, shortening the change management process.

II. WIRELESS NODE APPLICATION

A node sensor is a device that detects and responds to some type of input from the physical environment. This input could be light, heat, moisture, pressure, or any one of a great number of other environmental phenomena. The output is generally a signal that is converted to human-readable display at the sensor location or transmitted electronically over a network for reading or further processing.

A. Hardware Implementation

The application uses RSS2 Wireless Sensor Nodes on to which external sensors such as SHT25 and MS5611 are connected using the I2C interface.

Figure 1: The I2C interface of the RSS2 node.
Node configuration

This involves setting the tag mask, reporting interval, node name and aliases.

The Contiki operating system layers

Figure 1: The layers of contiki operating system

B. Data acquisition

Sensors including SHT25, MS5611 and MCP3424 are attached to RSS2 nodes, one at a time to capture temperature, humidity, pressure and to perform analog to digital conversions respectively the weather parameters.

The collected information is transmitted wirelessly to the sink node by broadcasting using IEEE 802.15.4 wireless protocol. For the data to be received, the sink node should be in close proximity with the rest of other RSS2 nodes and without any obstructions. The data captured by the RSS2 nodes will be accessed using SSH client installed on windows or Linux operating system.

C. Communication

We work with the RSS2 node based on the ATmega256 MCU, IEEE802.15.4 transceiver and an 8 channel 10bit ADC with an extended buffer storage.

On the protocol side, we use the IEEE802.15 standard on the link level and use the RIME

network protocol supporting periodical broadcasts from the RSS2 nodes to the sink node (which is a node connected to an FTDI cable).

The external devices will be attached to the RSS2 node from the I2C interface points.

The sink node (the RSS2 node connected to the raspberry pi) will be communicating with the raspberry pi via USB interface connection.

The results of the nodes are visualized using the SensorReader.

III. PROPRIETARY APPLICATION

This section surveys previous work that has been done in order to capture weather parameters using wireless sensor nodes.

A. Proprietary firmware

A firmware is a compiled program which is loaded on to the RSS2 node. The proprietary firmware [2] has been used in automatic weather stations for the capture and broadcast of weather parameters such as temperature, pressure, relative humidity, voltage, light among others. This application is also used for the configuration of RSS2 node that is setting the RSS2 node name, setting the tagmask i.e. T_MCU, LIGHT that produces a report mask of T_MCU=28.3 and LIGHT=70.3 and setting setting the reporting interval i.e. ri=6. The firmware also interacts

with sensd program, a program that performs the function of storing the data and sorting it respectively.

However, the application has the following drawbacks.

The application leaves out some functions which are required by the AWS for example setting alias, the source code is inaccessible making it impossible for developers to customize or modify the existing functions to meet the unique needs of AWS.

B. WIMEA-ICT-RSS2 firmware

This is a free and open source application for the RSS2 nodes that makes it possible for developers to customize the nodes to the functionality of AWS[1]. The application collects weather and link quality data from various sensors. Weather parameters collected include temperature, humidity and atmospheric pressure. On collecting this data, it is processed by transforming it into information that can be understood by meteorologists and stored in a central repository. A central repository is centralized location where all AWS send their data which can be accessed from the repository in various formats, for example graphs.

IV. METHODOLOGY

We achieved this by collecting requirements from existing documents. For example, the

SHT25 and MS5611 datasheets. They were mainly used to get addresses of both the SHT25 and MS5611 sensors that is the read and write addresses.

A. Experimental set up

This was carried out by setting up and monitoring the AWS which consisted of wireless sensor networks having the proprietary firmware. We attached several sensors to the RSS2 nodes on addition to its embedded sensors that capture different weather parameters. For example, temperature, light, pressure values are collected from the sensors and converted into human readable data. After processing weather data, the data is broadcast to the sink node connected to the raspberry pi. The combination of the sink and raspberry pi provided a gateway which was used to send data to the central repository via the internet.

Figure 2: Architecture of the Automatic Weather Station

I) Experimental findings

From the experiments we discovered that most of the users found it hard to use the command line-based application.

Issues that were discovered included the following:

- i. The application had limited functionalities.
- ii. The interface was not friendly.
- iii. Users were not comfortable with interacting with the command line interface.
- iv. The application runs on only Contiki operating system.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

We recommend that users read and understand the provided user manual before using the application.

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MAY GOB BLESS YOU ALL

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